

VERY LARGE ASSYMETRIC FAIRING DESIGN

John Higgins, Ph.D., P.E.
A.F. Research Laboratory
Space Vehicles Directorate
3550 Aberdeen Ave. SE
Kirtland AFB, NM 87117
john.higgins@kirtland.af.mil

Brandon Arritt
A.F. Research Laboratory
Space Vehicles Directorate
3550 Aberdeen Ave. SE
Kirtland AFB, NM87117
brandon.arritt@kirtland.af.mil

Tomoya Ochineru, Ph.D.
ATA Engineering, Inc.
1960 E. Grand Ave., Suite 560
El Segundo, CA 90245
tochiner@ata-e.com

SUMMARY

A very large asymmetric composite payload fairing (PLF) design was developed for unconventional payload geometry and sized on the Atlas V. The design meets strength, stability, and geometry constraints for an oversize demonstration payload. The final design was a composite sandwich structure that meets strength, buckling, flutter, thermal, and acoustic requirements.

Keywords: asymmetric fairing, finite element analysis, composites structures

INTRODUCTION

Tailored asymmetric payload fairings, such as the one shown in Figure 1, are advantageous compared to traditional axisymmetric payload fairings because it can be designed so that it 'shrink-wraps' around the geometry of the payload. This attribute is beneficial when launching relatively light but awkwardly shaped payloads such as unmanned aerial vehicles, parabolic antennas, etc. Currently, such payloads are launched using vehicles capable of lifting much heavier payloads than required. By using tailored asymmetric PLFs, such payloads may be launched using smaller vehicles thereby dramatically reducing costs. The challenge is to design and optimize the PLF geometry to minimize these aerodynamic loads so that it does not exceed the limits and control authority of the launch vehicle.

Figure 1. Diverse, tailored payload geometries

AERODYNAMIC LOAD PREDICTION & CONFIRMATION

The objective was to design a large payload fairing for use on the Atlas V Heavy Lift vehicle that can accommodate an unusual payload. Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) based geometric optimization was performed to evolve the design. Wind tunnel testing of a 2.5% scale fairing model was conducted at the Triumph Aerospace Trisonic Wind Tunnel (TWT) facilities in El Segundo, California. Furthermore, the agreement between the two test results shows that the data quality is good and tunnel conditions predictable. The most successful flow visualization test was the oil flow imagery. The results of analysis and test show very good qualitative agreement (see Figure 2)

Figure 2. Oil Flow test compared to CFD analysis

STRUCTURAL OPTIMIZATION

The large payload fairing is constructed of two sandwich panel halves which are connected to each other longitudinally through a frangible joint. The materials of the sandwich are MS35-4/AS4 plain weave carbon fiber for the faceskins and Rohacell 110 WF foam for the core. Nastran Solution 200 Design Optimization was utilized to size the sandwich structure of the large payload fairing. The variables optimized were faceskin ply thickness, faceskin ply orientation, and core thickness. The model was broken into three zones based on initial stress results from a single baseline layup that had positive margins with a 1 inch thick core. Figure 3 shows the three lay-up zones in blue, red, and yellow. After these three zones were created, each was allowed to optimize to a unique layup. The core thickness was forced to remain constant across all zones and the optimized layup was modified to maintain a balanced and symmetric laminate for production reasons.

Figure 3. Zones for Layup Optimization